

Co-thinking and Creation for STEAM diversity-gap reduction

2020-1-ES01-KA201-082601

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Dissemination and Exploitation Plan and Results

CreaSTEAM CONSORTIUM

May 2023

Amendment History

Version	Revision	Date	Author	Modification
1	0	9/02/2021	Virginia Kaladich, Giuseppe Maffeo, Francesco Graziani, Laura Belisari, Francesca Palma	Initial version
1	1	10/02/2021	Daniel Amo	Corrected some minor typographical errors.
2	0	11/02/2021	Daniel Amo	Added GOALS, defined in the 2030 UN Agenda and related to DIVERSITY
2	1	12/02/2021	Lucía García Holgado	CreaSTEAM Template applied
3	0	18/05/2023	David Fonseca	Data collected from dissemination reports

Table of contents

1. OBJECTIVES	4
2. LEVEL OF DISSEMINATION AND ACTIVITIES (LOCAL, REGIONAL, NATIONAL, EUROPEAN, AND INTERNATIONAL LEVEL): TARGET GROUPS AND BENEFICIARIES OF THE DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION .	5
2.1. INSIDE THE PARTNERSHIP	5
2.2. OUTSIDE THE PARTNERSHIP	5
3. IMPACT AND DISSEMINATION INDICATORS	7
4. PARTNERSHIP INVOLVEMENT	9
4.1. DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION NETWORK	9
4.2. DISSEMINATION PLAN ACTIONS BY PARTNERS AND COORDINATION TEAM	10
4.3. INVOLVEMENT OF ASSOCIATED PARTNERS, NOT FORMALLY PARTICIPATING IN THE PROJECT	10
5. COMMUNICATION CHANNELS AND ACTIVITIES	12
5.1. PAPER AND ONLINE WRITING FOR PRINT	12
5.2. MULTIMEDIA STRATEGY	12
5.2.1 <i>Project Website</i>	12
5.2.2 <i>Social Media</i>	13
5.2.3 <i>Promotional Emails</i>	14
5.2.4 <i>Newsletter</i>	14
5.3. THE EVENT STRATEGY	14
5.3.1 <i>Training Activity</i>	15
5.3.2 <i>Thematic Conferences</i>	16
5.3.3 <i>Local, regional, and European Meeting with Stakeholders</i>	16
5.3.4 <i>Final Multiplier Events</i>	16
6. DISSEMINATION AND OWNERSHIP OF RESULTS	17
7. CREATEAM VISUAL IDENTITY	18
8. SUSTAINABILITY AND VALORIZATION	20
9. REPORTING DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES	22
10. RESPONSIBILITIES	23
11. PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA IN DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	24
12. RESULTS AND ACTIVITY	25
13. CONCLUSIONS	35

1. Objectives

The current document is the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of the CreaSTEAM project, foreseen, elaborated, and implemented in the A3 activity. The Dissemination and Exploitation Plan aims to establish and run the visibility and communication infrastructure of the project so that all activities that will be carried out during the project's lifetime will be widely known with the highest possible visibility. To guarantee an effective promotion and exploitation of the project results, special attention will be given to making dissemination messages attractive and engaging for new stakeholders. Web-based tools, together with publications and event strategies, will be identified. Detailed information on timing, deadlines, dissemination products, and target groups will also be included in the plan.

The objectives of the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEP) are to:

- Provide useful information about project results and raise awareness about the existence of those results;
- Actively engage all partners in promoting the project in their countries and in particular in the EU region;
- Directly involve the target groups and stakeholders during the different phases of the project's development;
- Promote project sustainability, the capacity of the project to continue to exist and function beyond its end.

Sharing results, lessons learned and outcomes and findings beyond the participating organizations will enable a wider community to benefit from a CreaSTEAM project, as well as to promote the organization's efforts towards the objectives of Erasmus+, which attaches fundamental importance to the link between the Program and policies.

Taking the time to develop a comprehensive DEP will be advantageous for all the project consortium. As well as raising the profile of the partner organizations, dissemination and exploitation activities can often create new opportunities to extend the project and its results or develop new partnerships for the future. Successful dissemination and exploitation may also lead to external recognition of the work carried out adding further credit to it. Sharing the results will enable others to benefit from the activities and experiences of the CreaSTEAM project.

For the exploitation aspect, the objective of valorizing the CreaSTEAM project is to enable its results to become "sustainable". When the project comes to its end, specific measures will ensure that results are still available for usage by different groups. A strategy for the exploitation of project results after termination is defined as a valorization strategy, aiming to fulfill the goal of sustainability.

2. Level of dissemination and activities (local, regional, national, European, and international level): target groups and beneficiaries of the dissemination and exploitation

2.1. Inside the partnership

In terms of primary dissemination aim, the project has four targets that correspond to the distinct phases of its activities: students, teachers, educational public authorities, and organizations and initiatives related to promoting STEAM.

During the first year of the project, the main targets will be the organization and order of new initiatives related to STEAM, to involve some new informal/associated partners in the implementation of the STEAM-Labs during the end of the first year. Also, it is very important the dissemination of the project approach for involving the teachers in the partner schools, to recruit them to take part in the co-design of the STEAM-Labs. Moreover, during the first months of the project, the dissemination will be also focused on involving other schools from the network connected with the project. The recollection of the resources focused on STEAM strategies for diversity-gap reduction and their use in the process of STEAM-Lab creation will be another result to be disseminated in this first year, basically in educational forums.

During the second year, the focus will shift to recruiting students to participate in the STEAM-Labs, not only those directly involved by their teachers but also other students in the schools that want to participate in the STEAM-Lab after the formal activities of the curricula. Also, the public authorities and school bodies will be recruiting to join the CreaSTEAM network, as well as other universities and institutions focused on teacher training. In this sense, the main dissemination activities will be addressed to teachers of the schools, and other schools of the networks to present how the STEAM-Lab can address projects related to non-technical subjects, transversal projects between subjects and institutions, and of course, how this space can involve and improve the student's conception about STEAM vocations.

Moreover, during the whole project, the consortium will disseminate results, mainly to generate interest in the project amongst final beneficiary groups, increase demand for the projects' outputs, and thus create further incentives for the primary target groups to engage with the project. In particular, the aim is to provide awareness of the usefulness of the STEAM-Labs as a new dynamic space inside the schools. Second, the framework and the importance to foster diversity in the STEAM sector, and then willing to adopt it themselves for their context.

2.2. Outside the partnership

In addition to the dissemination activities directly associated with the achievement of the goals of the project, the dissemination plan will cover activities at three levels: local, regional/national, and international.

Locally the project is going to be disseminated to teachers and school bodies and cooperating with: associations, communities, non-profit organizations, companies, educational authorities, local bodies, and decision-makers involved in education promoting reducing the diversity gap in STEAM.

Regionally and nationally the project will reach a wider audience through school centers networking, HEIs cooperation, and exchange, schools working with different social groups and supporting them in the process of inclusion, or providing educational activities for them, e.g. training, workshops, social events, etc.

At the European and international levels, the target group will add university researchers and teachers, EU project managers, European educational authorities, and ascend locations of schools, public and private.

3. Impact and dissemination indicators

A set of quantitative and qualitative indicators will be measured, and analyzed, as a mixed approach. Some general indicators are identified that can be analyzed from a quantitative point of view but are very important to take attention to the qualitative perspective. For example, if our project is the base for one or two new European projects, from a quantitative point of view it seems a poor data, but from a qualitative view, is a very high impact because multiplies the impact and dissemination of the project.

The “likes”, “follows”, and “re-tweets” will be other indicators that will measure the capacity of impact and dissemination.

In particular, at the local level, the relevance of pilots in the schools:

- The number of schools involved (not only the partner schools): a minimum of 4.
- The number of teachers involved directly or indirectly through the activities of the project: at least 150 teachers.
- The number of activities and projects implemented in the STEAM-Labs: a minimum of 30.
- The number of students involved in the STEAM-Labs: a minimum of 200 students with 25% of participants with fewer opportunities.
- The number of students involved directly or indirectly in the activities of the project: a minimum of 550 students.

At regional and national levels:

- The number of participants in the multiplier events: a minimum of 100 participants.
- The number of organizations and initiatives achieved through dissemination activities: a minimum of 200.
- The number of schools interested in organizing workshops and activities following the resources and framework related to the STEAM-Labs, and approaches related to fostering the diversity gap.

At the International level:

- Participation in international conferences to share the main results of the project: a minimum of 4 conferences.
- Publication of the results in a formal way: a minimum of 2 indexed publications.
- Several other European countries achieved in the dissemination activities: a minimum of 4 different countries.

In addition to this, we will collect impact metrics relating to the dissemination activity in the project using dissemination logs, Google Analytics for online activity, and the feedback of the partners after each dissemination activity in a face-to-face way. This will include:

- Number of links to the project from other websites.
- Number of followers in the social media profiles of the project.
- Number of project-related interventions (posts/tweets...) in social media.
- Number of visitors to the project website.
- Number of repeat visitors to the project website.
- Average length of time spent on a website.
- Number of downloads of resources from the website.

- Number of requests for further information about the project.
- Number and nature of requests for conference speakers/presenters/workshop facilitators.
- Number of views of the articles of the project published in academic and other media.
- Translation by third parties of all or some of the resources into languages not included in the project.

Another indicator for measuring the achievements can be summarized as the following:

Quantitative indicators:

- List of participants in the 5 Transnational project meetings;
- List of participants in the 1 Short term joint staff training event.

Qualitative indicators:

- Reports from each partner institution;
- Dissemination of articles and texts in the media, both in paper and digital.

4. Partnership involvement

The partner consortium is formed by 2 universities, 3 local/regional/national educational associations, public institutions, and 2 schools, all involved in DEP Coordination Team¹:

- URL-La Salle
- USAL
- FIDAE
- Bursa MEM
- Sadettin Türkün Ortaokulu
- Clemens-Brentano-Europaschule
- Studienseminar GHRF

4.1. Dissemination and Exploitation Network

Dissemination activities will vary between partners, although in the context of homogeneous strategies and sources. It is important to consider what kinds of dissemination activities are fitted to each participating organization.

DRIVING PARTNERS IN THE PROJECT

- FIDAE as coordinator
- ALL PARTNERS involved

NETWORK BRANCHING – COORDINATION TEAM

FIDAE - La Salle URL – BURSA - STUDIENSEMINAR: responsible for creating a dissemination network, *in primis* with:

- ARLEP
- European Platform of Women Scientists (EPWS)
- Association for Women in Science and Technology
- Asociación de Mujeres Investigadoras y Tecnólogas (AMIT)
- Google Developer Groups (GDGs)
- State School Authority for the districts of Gießen and Vogelsbergkreis (Germany)
- European Catholic Schools Organization (ECNAIS, CEEC)

It is understood that, during the whole project, the consortium will disseminate results, mainly to generate interest in the project amongst final beneficiary groups, increase demand for the projects' outputs, and thus create further incentives for the primary target groups to engage with the project.

¹ Each partner indicates one or more contact persons for DEP.

All of the results of the project are relevant for dissemination, and it will be important that the CreaSTEAM framework is a whole since it will derive much of its value from the cascade approach both inside the partnership and outside.

All partners have made a clear commitment to participation in the dissemination of the work and to look for synergies with other stakeholders who may be working on projects and initiatives with similar objectives where collaboration may be valuable. It is perhaps important to note that some members of the consortium are in touch with researchers, communities, and associations outside Europe who are working on parallel lines and with whom it might be fruitful to collaborate. Contacts already exist and these possibilities will be explored during and beyond the project.

4.2. Dissemination Plan Actions by Partners and Coordination Team

The DEP coordination team, to assure good impact, focus on synchronizing publication by partners on important dates, following these lines of action concerning:

1. Partners
 - a. Make things easy for partners
 - b. Request to fulfill the Dissemination Social Media Profiles document attached (annex 1). This will help to track their publications and summarize impact when needed **only under hashtag #CreaSTEAM**.
 - c. Remember to publish
 - i. When important dates approach for Project Activities milestones regarding the "Project Management Plan"
 - ii. **In advance and repeatedly** when the dissemination report date approaches.
 - d. Request them to fulfill the Dissemination Activities Report (attached and filled with 2 examples) for those important activities, and not for every message published on social media
2. DEP Coordination team
 - a. Assure that partners fulfill the Dissemination of Social Media Profiles
 - b. Assure that partners fulfill the Dissemination Activities Report (annex 2) adequately and on time
 - c. Remember partners to publish when needed
 - d. Track partner's social media profiles to summarize the impact in the Dissemination Activities Report.

4.3. Involvement of associated partners, not formally participating in the project

Association for Women in Science and Technology (<https://www.amit-es.org/>), Asociación de Mujeres Investigadoras y Tecnólogas (AMIT) in Spanish, is a non-governmental, nonprofit association composed of researchers and technologists from various disciplines that develop their research, technology, or science management in public and private Spanish research organizations and centers. Also, it is part of the European Platform of Women Scientists (EPWS). The association was born created to cover the need to defend the interests and equal rights and opportunities of Spanish researchers and

technologists. AMIT aims to be a voice, discussion forum, and support network for all people aware that we have of the need to work together. Only this way then will we achieve the full participation of women in Research, Science, and Technology. Its main objective is to promote equal access for women to research activity in all branches of knowledge and the technology sector. In particular: Promote equality between women and men in access to research activity in all scientific, technological, and humanities fields. Sensitize our environment and society in general about situations of discrimination and the mechanisms to lead deal with it them. Achieve equal opportunities throughout the career for women researchers and technologists in both the public and private sectors. Prepare recommendations and collaborate with other European and international organizations to facilitate the advancement of women in Science. Make visible the scientists and the results of their work. In general, promote compliance with the recommendations of the European Commission to achieve gender equality and the Spanish regulations contained in the

Organic Law for Effective Equality between Women and Men and the development of the gender aspect included in the Spanish Law of Science.

On the other hand, Tech&Ladies (<http://techandladies.com/>) is a Spanish project promoted by women organizers of Google Developer Groups (GDGs) in Spain and the collaboration of several women experts in technology. Its main purpose is to give visibility to women who create and work in technology. More specifically its objectives are: Acknowledge women's issues when connecting with technology and finding solutions to them; Provide training; Disclose patterns of women in technology, to have female references; Get young girls interested in pursuing a career in technology.

Distrito ARLEP is the association of Lasallian schools of Spain, Portugal, and Andorra. Because of the direct contact with schools of childhood, primary, secondary, bachelor, VET, and Universities, its main function as an associate partner is to disseminate the project and establish relations between schools and the project members to develop the project in the schools in future years, considering that the main objectives of the project are to be identified as some priority actions to develop in the schools in a close future.

Furthermore, the State School Authority for the districts of Gießen and Vogelsbergkreis (Germany), a public authority to ensure the quality of school work, the comparability of qualifications, and the permeability of educational programs in the Gießen and Vogelsberg districts. This authority has a direct connection with the German school involved in the project and the public institutions to prepare teachers (STUDIENSEMINAR). This associated partner will support the identification of practices and collaborate in the co-creation of the STEAM-Labs to ensure that the approach could be replicated in other schools in the region.

Finally, FIDAE, in addition to being an institutional interlocutor of the Italian Ministry of Education and its regional branches, has association and collaboration relationships with European networks of Catholic schools, such as ECNAIS (European Council of National Associations of Independent Schools) and CEEC (European Committee for Catholic Education). FIDAE will promote the activities and results of the project in its networks.

5. Communication Channels and Activities

The dissemination and exploitation activities will be carried out following 3 main strategies:

- *The paper and online writing for print* (project postcards, leaflets, press releases, scientific papers)
- *The Multimedia Strategy* (project website, social media, news, video production, European Platforms, etc.)
- *The Event Strategy* (training, key thematic conferences, forums, events, final workshop, etc.)

This wide dissemination approach will support the "cascading effect", motivating others to use the results for their projects and changes in their institutions.

5.1. Paper and online writing for print

Online writing and printed materials are essential for promotional purposes. Dissemination materials will be produced according to the perceived needs of the Consortium. Project postcards and flyers in particular can be produced reasonably cheaply and in large quantities, therefore readily lending themselves to large-scale communicative purposes.

Partners will distribute branding materials on a wide scale, via the web included, targeting the school's owner, manager and teachers, students, parents, university managers and teachers, stakeholders, and policymakers at national, regional, and international levels.

Regarding the project graphical identity, the design of the overall graphical identity of the project and production of branding materials for dissemination purposes (project logo, templates for deliverables, standard project presentation, project postcard, leaflets, posters, rolls up, etc.) will be in English. This includes the design of the following documents:

- Conception of the information and scientific documents concerning the project CreaSTEAM (publication of the results in a formal way: a minimum of 2 indexed publications, etc.)
- Press releases on the occasion of key events or achievements will be created and disseminated within project partners' networks. Press releases may occur to: introduce the project and the upcoming meetings, launch the training activities, promote the multiplier events of the project;
- Project brochure to communicate the project to specific target groups and communicate the objectives and expected results will be designed and realized
- Flyers.
- Posters.

5.2. Multimedia Strategy

For Multimedia Strategy we intend dissemination happening through online tools, news, video production, online sharing, social media, etc, to spread the word about the project in a quick, wide, effective, and powerful way. The ability of these media to facilitate communication is tremendous, and they allow them to reach single target stakeholders as well as communities and bigger audiences.

5.2.1 Project Website

The project website will serve as the dissemination hub, (indeed this is its main focus) where all news and resources will be available and from there syndicated out to a range of social media groups.

The CreaSTEAM project website is available at the following address: <https://creasteam.eu/>.

The project website is intended to provide a first level of information about the scope and activities of the CreaSTEAM project. Main achievements and events will be available to all.

Google Analytics is used to continually measure the performance and activity of visitors on the CreaSTEAM website, so that impact can be easily assessed and statistics available.

The image below presents the structure of the project website: a page dedicated to presenting an overview of the project, a page for Partners, a page dedicated to the idea, and a page with the CreaSTEAM contacts.

5.2.2 Social Media

In addition to the project website, Social Media will also be used to disseminate events and achievements, as well as to promote discussions and engage teachers, parents, principals, researchers, stakeholders, schools, and university staff.

Social networks are useful tools for establishing continuous interaction with project stakeholders, for keeping daily interest in project initiatives and events, and for sharing key achievements. The main objectives of social media are:

- Spreading project information, activities, and results
- Broaden the outreach of CreaSTEAM

- Exchanging experiences
- Allowing the creation of a very interactive dissemination
- Analysis of the audience feedback to adjust the communication strategy

All partners agreed, during the kick-off meeting, about do not create specific social networks for the project, in this way, the Project website will be the main space to share the progress and results of the project and the partners will use their social networks to spread the word.

The hashtag of the Project for the social networks is #CreaSTEAM.

5.2.3 Promotional Emails

Project partners will draw and send Information/Promotion emails devoted to the different project stakeholders to inform them about relevant events. The emails are intended to provide an appealing message for attracting the attention and interest of the recipients. To reach this goal, all promotional emails will be sent with the visual identity of the CreaSTEAM project (in terms of logo, colors, and structure).

All partners are invited to share Information/Promotion emails within their networks.

5.2.4 Newsletter

The news will be produced and published by all Partners regularly, in conjunction with key results and events. Partners are invited to share project news within their network of contacts and on their website.

In addition, 4 newsletters will also be produced and distributed. An online newsletter is an effective way to keep interested parties informed about the project's progress, achieved results, and relevant events at local and international levels. The main project target is teachers, students, parents, academics and managers, education institutions, researchers, and stakeholders in the field of secondary and higher education, etc. The main channel of distribution will be the Partner network of contacts. Participation in the project of large associations, universities, and school institutions will ensure a wide project outreach. The main goal will be to spotlight the project and its main initiatives to a large interested audience.

Each news/newsletter should include:

- Basic information about the project
- Key Information about the result achieved or the event to be promoted
- Contacts and useful resources.

5.3. The Event Strategy

An effective dissemination plan must include the organization of, and participation in, key events and thematic conferences. Presenting the CreaSTEAM project to an audience will be essential to:

- Engage stakeholders through discussion and confrontation
- Present the project as a living creature, involving the audience in its development
- Understand the response of target groups to the project proposals
- Measure the impact of project outcomes
- Receive feedback and inputs for future implementation.

5.3.1 Training Activity

The training activity will be designed to approach STEAM concepts to teachers for better implementation in their classes and projects and thus conceived this activity is intimately connected to disseminating and exploiting the contents and results of the project. The main idea is that by using the STEAM-Labs and all their options, we can change the point of view of the teachers and their future students related to complex areas such as Engineering, Science, and Technological systems, and the way to use all types of projects to accomplish the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) -also known as the Global Goals adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015- and related to diversity-gap: Quality education, Gender equality, Industry, innovation, and infrastructure, and Reduce inequalities. The training will be focused on seven points:

1. How to develop robotics into their school's curriculum.
2. How to use mobile devices for social projects, data collection, and visualization.
3. How to develop maker spaces for prototyping.
4. How to develop advanced visualization using Augmented and Virtual Reality Low-Cost devices.
5. How to develop multimedia systems to connect the models and data developed in physical and virtual systems.
6. How to expand the use of digital technologies and new educational methods using them into more classical subjects and contents.
7. How to merge content, local projects, digital media, and prototyping for new communication methods with society.

These topics are addressed to change the point of view of teachers and students related to the most complex issues in STEAM. Addressing STEAM approaches for all types of educational, social, and diversity projects is funny, and easy and creates more motivation than using a classical methodology. Some starting ideas to develop the pilot projects will be:

- a) Design, prototyping, and programming of environmental sensors/micro-robots to visualize indicators like noise, air conditions, illuminations, etc.
- b) Using AR and VR for cultural heritage restitution of ancient buildings and environments for cultural education and visual education.
- c) Basic programming and use of mobile devices for data collection, visualization, and analysis of social, cultural, scientific, usability, or accessibility projects.

These three ideas can be developed in the STEAM-Labs and are addressing issues that can be identified with students and groups affected by diversity gap indicators. How to enroll the students in the STEAM approach to improve STEAM vocation is the key concept and the need is to explain the approach to the students... it is not necessary to live in a great city or in a first-world country to study or develop these types of projects, with the STEAM-Lab it is possible with low few resources.

The objectives of this training are addressed:

1. Training and empowering secondary teachers (or equivalent level), in the use of the recommended STEAM-Labs and tools (robotics, maker spaces, AR and VR systems, using mobile devices for educational projects and assessment, computational thinking, etc.) validated by the studied study on continuous development in O2 (The teacher training will be after identifying best practices and having a first approximation of the initiatives map. The training will focus on skills and competencies to define the action plan for schools with different socio-cultural backgrounds students).

2. How to manage diversity variables in STEAM educational projects. The aim is to select those activities and best practices that fit better for the context of the school and the potential students involved. Although schools have experience defining and implementing new curricula, they need some guidelines to define the action plan focused on diversity.
3. Visit to the educational technology facilities of 2 leading schools of the La Salle network in Barcelona, and exchange STEAM experiences between Spanish teachers and the rest of the partners and teachers of the project (Turkey, Germany, and Italy).
4. Promote team spirit among the group of teachers and members of the project, with the possibility of establishing new connections in the international network of schools that are addressing STEAM projects.

5.3.2 Thematic Conferences

Dissemination activities through presentations at events. All the partners participate regularly in a range of different events to support Youth. Furthermore, many of the partners organize their events such as the International Conference Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality (USAL), or the Educational Innovation Seminars (URL), and will disseminate the project through these channels. The project partners, especially URL-La Salle, FIDAE, Bursa MEM, and USAL are habitually present in a range of other events relating to education, youth, and gender, and these represent valuable entry points for disseminating the CreaSTEAM outcomes.

5.3.3 Local, regional, and European Meeting with Stakeholders

Consultation with stakeholders will be performed by partners for dissemination and long-term planning. Face-to-face communication is considered a must for visibility and dissemination and is intended not only as **formal meetings** but also as **informal meetings**. Indeed, informal interactive and flexible meetings with stakeholders are as important as official consultations, as to let partners get direct feedback and inputs. The idea is to identify and get in contact with several stakeholders interested in supporting the activities of the project.

At the European level, the project will be presented during seminars and face-to-face presentations within Erasmus+ multiplier events and kick-off meetings of other projects related to STEAM at schools in general, during international conferences and seminars.

5.3.4 Final Multiplier Events

There will be organized four multiplier events and they will be announced and reviewed in local media (ex. radio, press, and online local portals on culture or education). We expect about 100 participants (at least 25 from each country partner institution) in the multiplier events held at the end of the project (September 2020), to present the project and promote all the project results and Intellectual Outputs.

The four multiplier events are:

- E1. STEAM-Labs workshop Spain. Lead by USAL.
- E2. STEAM-Labs workshop Italy. Lead by FIDAE.
- E3. STEAM-Labs workshop Turkey. Lead by Bursa MEM.
- E4. STEAM-Labs workshop Germany. Lead by Studienseminar GHRF.

6. Dissemination and ownership of results

For the development and dissemination process of the project, it has been established in the association agreement that:

- A website with the project data and main results, with an Intranet where the work data, projects, and contents in the creation of the finished products, as well as the data analysis, will be published in OPEN-ACCESS.
- The Erasmus + Project Results Platform will be used as a valuable repository to access the projects funded under the program as well as the contact information of the grantee organizations. Also, it will be useful for the compilation of good practices.
- the School Education Gateway (SEG), a European online platform for school education, would be a preferable tool for use in the project. In this regard, the platform offers plenty of resources to enhance teachers' knowledge, skills, and attitudes to improve their current practices and, thus, have an impact on their learners' performance.
- Dissemination of results will be on social networks and other sites, both the partner's own, as well such as those that group the member centers of the association: FIDAE, ARLEP, USAL, BURSA, or STUDIENSEMINAR, always in OPEN-ACCESS.
- URL-LaSalle will evaluate the Open Access possibilities for the project, ensuring the maximum diffusion of the results and data generated among the scientific community, academia, and society in general, using their online office: <https://www.url.edu/ca/recerca-i-innovacio/la-recerca-la-url/ciencia-oberta>.

7. CreaSTEAM visual identity

At the beginning of the project, Partners focused on defining the project vision, as clearly expressed on the project website (<https://creasteam.eu/>). Along with the definition of the project identity in terms of mission and goals, Partners also developed the project's visual identity. Several suggestions for the project logo were developed by the project Coordinator and presented to the Consortium members.

The following logo is the final one selected by the project Coordinator and all Partners:

Furthermore, during the Kick-off Meeting Online (14, 15 & 18 January 2021) of the project it was agreed to:

- Partners will provide the information for the website through the Management Platform
- All partners agree on the hashtag of the Project for the social networks: #CreaSTEAM
- All partners agree about do not create specific social networks for the project, in this way, the Project website will be the main space to share the progress and results of the project and the partners will use their social networks to spread the Word.

Requirements on the application of the visual identity of the EU on products and publication

Use of Erasmus+ Logo

The use of the Erasmus+ logo is compulsory (no changes).

Any project-related event or activity should specify that it is funded by EU Erasmus+ Programme any publication should include the following sentence:

"The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents which reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein."

More information is available at:

- https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/about-eacea/visual-identity_en
- <http://sepie.es/comunicacion/imagen.html>

All the information and tools are available in the Moodle platform (<https://polis.grial.eu/>): A3. *Dissemination and exploitation.*

8. Sustainability and Valorization

Sustainability is the capacity of the project to continue to exist and function beyond the end of the contract. The project results are used and exploited continuously. Sustainability of results means the use and exploitation of results in the long term.

'Valorization' is the French term for dissemination and exploitation of results, also used in the European context. Valorization activities are required to ensure that the results of the Erasmus+ are appropriately recognized, demonstrated, and implemented on a wide scale.

All intellectual outputs will be available on the project website. First, the co-design of the STEAM-Labs (IO1) will be published in open access. Regarding the second output, the collection of electronic resources that compose the CreaSTEAM framework will be available on the project website (the initiatives map, the activity packages, the methodology, and the guidelines for parents).

Moreover, resources will be available as separate resources for downloading.

The resources on the website will also be readily available and freely accessible from the website, and posts on social media will link back to the website to ensure that the open availability is transparent to all. Also, the consortium will share the public results and documents in an institutional repository and in Zenodo with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make them easily and uniquely citable.

Both the project website itself and the open-access strategy described above will be available continuously after the end of the project's lifetime. The website will be maintained indefinitely for the schools who will participate, seeing it as central to our activity, which, it should be emphasized, dates back to long before this particular project. In this sense, the continuing availability of this work is central to the activity of the partners, which is a strong guarantee of the longevity of the results. The other partners, with their focus on education and research, also have a strong interest in the sustainability of the outcomes as part of their research work.

It is important to mention that during that time, it will not remain static but will be periodically updated with content and we will continue to monitor usage throughout this period. There will also be a link to and from the other sites of the partners and partner organizations.

All the content and resources produced by the project will therefore continue to be fully available to the general public and researchers after the end of the funding period.

In addition to this, the partnership aims to continue to use, develop and promote the outputs developed in the project in their organizations, since for each of them this approach is necessary to introduce the challenges associated to reduce diversity and the gender gap in STEAM. Furthermore, the activity of the partners both during and after the project is aimed to promote the uptake of the approach above and beyond the scope of the consortium.

Another key aspect of the continued availability and uptake of the project results is that the partners, as part of their ongoing activity, participate regularly in, and also organize annual events in their fields, and in the activities of their range of networks and associations, and these conform a continuous audience for the outputs of the project. While the project duration is finite, these organizations continue their activity beyond the project lifetime, and participation by the partners in these guarantees that the stakeholders involved will continue to be reached.

While some European projects set up a specific organism, an Association, or Foundation, to guarantee sustainability, this is not the case in CreaSTEAM. The project aims to implement STEAM-Labs at schools as a dynamic space to foster diversity in STEAM through the development of STEAM competencies, digital competence, and soft skills.

The URL-La Salle collaborate with Distrito ARLEP to implement the first approach of the Labs in the schools of the network, the GRIAL Research Group at the University of Salamanca in collaboration with AMIT and Tech&Ladies already promotes diversity and gender balance in STEAM; FIDAE, Stuidenseminar, and Bursa MEM are a network themselves. This means that early in the project the organizational infrastructure to ensure the sustainability of the project results will already be in place.

As regards the plans for sustainability, these will be discussed during the project, but initial draft plans are as follows. CreaSTEAM outputs will be publicly available for anyone without any extra costs. Additionally, whatever is going to be developed within this project will be prepared in a downloadable English version, hence we believe that the teachers' community will benefit from its output for a longer time sharing the resources and experience within the academic network, adult education societies, etc.

The partners involved in this project will also refer to this project and its results when planning future collaborative initiatives on local, regional, and international levels. The lessons learned collected in this project will be applied in the future development of activities in innovative teaching methods both in the schools and in future teachers' training for bridging the diversity gap and promoting gender balance in STEAM.

9. Reporting Dissemination and Exploitation activities

Reports on dissemination and exploitation plan to assess the success and impact will be produced in months 7, 12, 17, and 24 covering all dissemination activities carried out during the project, both online and others. It will be led by FIDAE. All partners will be fully involved. The draft version of the reports will be presented during the transnational meetings and delivered after them to include the comments and information provided during the meeting.

The actions related to reporting, presentations of results, data protection, and any other documentation that might be required by the European Agency will be carefully monitored.

10. Responsibilities

Each project partner has committed to comply with the provisions contained in the PARTNERSHIP AGREEMENT FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PROJECT, which states:

- Article 6. Responsibilities.

1) Towards the Coordinator and the PSB (Permanent Supervisory Board), each Party hereby undertakes:

...

- (h) to inform about the intention to disseminate, either to the general public or third parties not represented in the PSB, the activities or the results obtained within the Project, including the publication of papers or articles, no matter their format. Prior notice of any planned dissemination shall be given at least thirty (30) days before the communication. Any objection to the planned dissemination shall be made in writing to the Coordinator and any Party concerned within thirty (30) days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the dissemination is permitted.

11. Processing of personal data in dissemination activities

Each Partner/Beneficiary involved in dissemination activity shall be controller, in the terms of article 4.7 of the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April 2016), for processing of the personal data of the participants in the activities organized by them. Each Partner/Beneficiary shall inform the participants about the purpose of the collection of personal data, their rights, and the recipients, or categories of recipients, of the personal data. In this regard, they will be informed that the data of participants will be shared with the CreaSTEAM Coordinator project and its Affiliated Entities, so that, in compliance with any legal obligation, they can inform the Erasmus+ Agency of the participants in the activities.

Each Partner/Beneficiary, to disseminate the activities or project results, past, present, or future, before using personal data, including images, photos, videos, etc., must acquire consent to use the data, giving adequate information on the use of data collected.

12. Results and Activity

Next, and as a justification of the dissemination activity, we will present the results obtained. In this sense, and in addition to the main digital channel used throughout the project, the CreaSTEAM website (<https://creasteam.eu/>), other channels have been created that have allowed the consortium to upload all the activities carried out in the open, such as the YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@creasteam4135>) and the CreaSTEAM space in the Open Access Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/search?page=2&size=20&q=creasteam#>). As activities and news were produced, the Twitter channel was also used, using the hashtag [#CreaSTEAM_proj](https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj) (https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj).

In addition, the partners have carried out face-to-face and digital actions through their social networks to expand the impact of the project. In chronological order, the table in this section shows the actions carried out, their objective, target audience, potential attendees, and digital links to related news. In this sense, in addition to the digital resources initially mentioned, two news environments were activated to promote information about the project in two of the networks that initially did not contribute schools to the project, that of ARLEP in Spain, to which URL-La Salle belongs (<https://blogs.salleurl.edu/ca/technology-learning>), and the FIDAE in Italy (<https://www.fidae.it/ep-creasteam-2020-2022/>).

The result of the Multiplier Events has been very relevant, with more than 200 attendees overall, well above the project's forecast. Either in part or in full, the videos of the MEs are available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=w90On3N67oA&list=PLjFtx3NivtmaKdc6qloWTFkheQGa0A4HM>

In addition, the project description, designs, and results have been published in educational innovation and research forums. In this sense, in addition to various participations in conferences, book chapters and articles have been published in indexed journals that can be found indexed in: <https://creasteam.eu/publications-and-presentations/>

Currently, and within the project justification period, the project continues to have an impact at international level. Not only a new Erasmus + KA2 project (DivinSTEAM, continuation of CreaSTEAM but focused on disabilities and mental disorders) has been submitted for the period 2023-2026 with 14 partners from Italy, Turkey, Portugal, and Spain, but several partners have participated in up to 3 new STEAM proposals of this program. In addition, the project members URL and USAL have been contacted to be part of new EU-funded project proposals for the 2023 call, and for example, have been visited by the Foundation for Partnership and Civil Society Development from Pula (Croatia) to be informed about the scope of CreaSTEAM to implement it in their field of action, or have been invited to participate in the meeting of the Society Of Women Engineers (SWE) to be held in Barcelona on 25-26 May 2023 at the STEM Education Research Roundtable, all aspects that demonstrate the scope of the dissemination of the project.

Activity	Date	Brief Description	Target Group	# of people reached	Other data
Presentation of the project. USAL	16/10/2020	Dissemination of the project in GRIAL website. Presentation of the project using social media channels	General public	75	https://grial.usal.es/news/concedida-financiacion-C3%B3n-para-desarrollar-el-proyecto-creasteam-bajo-el-programa-erasmus-2020

Activity	Date	Brief Description	Target Group	# of people reached	Other data
Presentation of the project, USAL	16/10/2020	Dissemination of the project in social media. Presentation of the project using social media channels	General public	479	https://twitter.com/grial_usal/status/1317132919304032257
Presentation of CreaSTEAM. URL_La Salle + USAL	01/12/2020	The dissemination project aims to engage stakeholders and target groups, etc. A website with overall information regarding the CreaSTEAM project	press, media, general public	200	https://creasteam.eu
Meeting inside the Sadettin Türkün Ortaokulu. BURSA + Sadettin	13/10/2020	Sharing the project with the project team in the Research and Development Unit.	Teachers/managers	20	
Presentation of the project. URL	12/01/2021	The dissemination project aims through social media	Presentation of the project using social media channels	4.390	
Presentation of the project. URL	12/01/2021	Dissemination project aims through La Salle Blog	Presentation of the project by blogging		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/ca/conc-essio-del-financament-al-desenvolupament-de-el-proje-creasteam-en-el-marc-de-el-proje
Presentation of the project - Kick off. USAL	14/01/2021	Dissemination of the project kick-off meeting in social media. Presentation of the project using social media channels	General public	4.305	https://twitter.com/alicciagh/status/134964605500969222?s=21
Creation of CreaSTEAM project section on fidae.it website. FIDAE	14/01/2021	Webpage created in Italian to introduce CreaSTEAM project to our schools. Description, partners and links are provided. This will be the homepage of a dedicated section	website users, Italian catholic schools	250 unique visitors at 31 may 2021	https://bit.ly/2YH7Pi4
Sharing the project's activities, such as meeting photos of project (twitter). BURSA + Sadettin	14/01/2021	Needs for training	Teachers/managers	20	

Activity	Date	Brief Description	Target Group	# of people reached	Other data
Press release about CreaSteam Project. FIDAE	15/01/2021	Description of the project and a statement of Fidae President Virginia Kaladich. Publication on national magazines and websites	press agencies		https://bit.ly/3tx06lQ bit.ly/3vCScb8 t.ly/YR3H https://educazione.chiesacattolica.it/fidae-al-via-il-progetto-erasmus-creasteam/
Presentation of the project. USAL	18/01/2021	Dissemination of the project in the "Master's degree in Information and Communication Technologies for Digital Education and Learning" of the Nebrija University. Presentation of the project using the website as an example of educational innovation approaches	Future teachers and on-service teachers	51	No pictures because it does not allow taking screenshots
Presentation of the project. USAL	26/01/2021	Dissemination of the project in the "Master's degree in Information and Communication Technologies for Digital Education and Learning" of the Nebrija University. Presentation of the project using the website as an example of educational innovation approaches	Future teachers and on-service teachers	49	No pictures because it does not allow taking screenshots
Presentation of the project. URL_La Salle+ USAL	01/12/2021	Dissemination project aims through social media. Presentation of the project using social media channels	press, media, general public	4.390	
Presentation of the project: Facebook post. FIDAE	01/02/2021	Description of the project, launching the hashtag #CREASTEAM	Fidae Facebook followers	1040 Followers	
Presentation of the project. URL	27/1/2021	Description of the project to the head of Pedagogy of Catalan La Salle Schools.	La Salle Schools	150	It was agreed to propose to 3 schools in the network of 17 schools.
Newsletter to all our members with a presentation of the project. FIDAE	28/01/2021	Newsletter	Fidae Members	2000 catholic schools	

Activity	Date	Brief Description	Target Group	# of people reached	Other data
Mention the project. USAL	11/02/2021	Sharing the aim of the project in the round table of the "Las II Jornadas Mujer y Niña en la Ciencia". Presentation of the project and the relation with another European project, W-STEM	General public	144	https://youtu.be/qVNG3n-gKe4
Contact to La Salle schools. URL	12/02/2021	Contact to 3 La Salle schools to participate in CreaSTEAM. Used tools: Email, phone calls.	Teachers/managers	150	
Dissemination Meeting with School (Uluslararası Murad Hüdavendigâr High School). BURSA + Sadettin	24/02/2021	Meeting Teachers/managers Schools with Steam Practices. Introducing CreaSTEAM Project so that we can find associated schools	Teachers/managers /students	200	
Dissemination Meeting with School (Özel Bahçeşehir School) BURSA + Sadettin	21/03/2021	Meeting Teachers/managers Schools with Steam Practices. Introducing CreaSTEAM Project so that we can find associated schools	Teachers/managers /students	300	https://twitter.com/Volchox/status/137371767385553540?s=20
Monitoring meeting. URL	26/03/2021	Dissemination of the monitoring meeting	Presentation of the review of initiatives map and activities to define the STEAM-Lab.	Press, media, general public	https://blogs.salleurl.edu/en/monitoring-meeting-creasteam
Mention the project. USAL	20/04/2021	Sharing the aim of the project in an international event "Cumbre Internacional Virtual de Inteligencia y Talento CIVIT 2021". Presentation of the project and the relation with another European project, W-STEM	General public	400	

Activity	Date	Brief Description	Target Group	# of people reached	Other data
Dissemination Meeting with School (Özel Mesafe VET) BURSA + Sadettin	20/4/2021	Meeting Teachers/managers Schools with Steam Practices. Introducing CreaSTEAM Project so that we can find associated schools	Teachers/managers /students	200	https://twitter.com/Volchox/status/1384576784553979908?s=20
1st Day Teacher Training. URL	15/05/2021	Dissemination of the teacher training. First day of Training for teachers of associated schools	social media		https://twitter.com/fonsi1x2/status/1393390653158084611?s=20
2nd Day Teacher Training. URL	21/05/2021	Dissemination of the teacher training. The second day of Training for teachers of associated schools	social media	1263	https://twitter.com/danielamof/status/1395715049487020035?s=20
Registration of our STEAM-Lab course for the next school year. CBES	27/5/2021	Brief description of our new project for the students who have to select an optional course for the next school year	All 8th-graders	Around 100 students	
Meeting with the SISTERSLAB. USAL	27/05/2021	Sisterslab is an association that empowers women in the field of Steam, with Zoom meeting "We Had" brainstorming about initiatives map and helped us to reach related initiatives.	associations, designers, volunteers, engineers, and project coordinators.	25	
Teacher training. URL	28/05/2021	Dissemination of the teacher training. Training to teachers of associated schools	press, media, general public		https://www.salleurl.edu/en/teacher-training-sessions-within-creasteam-project
Article for our homepage. CBES	31/05/2021	Information for the whole school and all interested people	School and interested people	Everybody who looks up the homepage	
Video about our new project for the homepage and Instagram account. CBES	week from 7.-11.6.21	Information for the whole school, but especially for the students who have to select their optional course	School, 8th-graders	Everybody who looks up the homepage	
Creation of CreaSTEAM project section on sabinianum.com website (associated school). FIDAE	5/7/2021	Sabinianum created an article with a video presentation and a description of CreaSTEAM project	website users, families of children enrolled in school		bit.ly/3yr6zQW

Activity	Date	Brief Description	Target Group	# of people reached	Other data
FIDAE National Council	27-30/08/2021	Illustration of the project and information on its outputs. It is the annual meeting of FIDAE	Fidae National Council Members and other School Principals	40	
3rd PSB Meeting. URL	14/09/2021	Dissemination PSB Meeting. Summary of the third PSB Meeting where key points are presented	social media	752	https://twitter.com/danielamof/status/1437714903373078532?s=20
Training pills. URL	17/09/2021	Dissemination of training pills. Blog publication of training pills	press, media, general public		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/en/training-pills
YouTube Channel. URL	21/09/2021	Dissemination of training pills. Publication of training pills videos	social media	10	CreaSTEAM - YouTube
YouTube Channel. URL	21/09/2021	Dissemination of training pills. Blog publication of YouTube channel	press, media, general public		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/ca/cana-i-de-youtube-i-videos-training-pills
Contact with new schools. URL	21/09/2021	Dissemination to schools and acquisition. Important contact was made with Consejería de Educación de Canarias to migrate schools with FAB-LAB in conversion to STEAM-LAB.	Govern, entities, and organizations	50	https://twitter.com/danielamof/status/1440260809821618182?s=20
Creation of CreaSTEAM project section on the web (associated school). FIDAE	25/9/2021	Istituto Gonzaga created an article with a description of the CreaSTEAM project:	Website users, families of children enrolled in school		https://gonzagascuola.it/crea-stem-al-gonzaga/
3rd PSB Meeting. URL	29/09/2021	Dissemination PSB Meeting. Summary of the third PSB Meeting where the next steps are presented	Press, media, general public		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/en/youtube-channel-and-training-pills-videos
First face-to-face meeting Giessen. URL	07/10/2021	Dissemination of Giessen Transnational Meeting. Summary of Giessen Transnational Meeting	press, media, general public		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/empozamos-la-primera-reunion-cara-cara-del-proyecto-creasteam-0
Teacher training. URL	26/11/2021	Dissemination to teachers. Schools of ARLE - Valencia Area	Teachers	30	https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/difusion-del-proyecto-creasteam-en-valencia https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj/status/1464235759674744832?s=20&t=9PeXqPGs70HBUIAWbyt1wA
Dissemination. URL	06/11/2021	Dissemination to scientific community. TEEM21 Conference	Scientific Community	400	https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/presentacion-del-proyecto-creasteam-en-la-novena-edicion-del-teem https://twitter.com/fonsi1x2/status/1583455809295380480?s=20&t=MvZHCyI9Uv3_QXyKivGbg

Activity	Date	Brief Description	Target Group	# of people reached	Other data
Teacher training. URL	04/11/2021	Dissemination to teachers. Schools of ALRPE Andalusian area	Teachers	35	https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/dise-minacion-profesorado-de-salle-sevilla-del-proyecto-creasteam https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj/status/1457993626894622720?s=20&t=9PeXqPGs70HBUIAWby1wA
Teacher training. URL	28/10/2021	Dissemination to teachers. Schools of ARLEP, Balearic Islands	Teachers	30	https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/dise-minacion-en-palma-de-mallorca-del-proyecto-creasteam
Dissemination. URL	28/10/2021	Dissemination to scientific community. CINAIC21 Conference	Scientific Community	300	https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/informacion-del-proyecto-creasteam-en-el-congreso-cinaic https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj/status/1457631237884059649?s=20&t=9PeXqPGs70HBUIAWby1wA
First CreaSTEAM newsletter. URL	16/12/2021	Dissemination of CreaSTEAM news. Summary of news	press, media, general public		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/se-envia-el-primero-newsletter-del-proyecto-creasteam https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj/status/1471529063365976067?s=20&t=9PeXqPGs70HBUIAWby1wA
CreaSTEAM time extension. URL	09/02/2022	Dissemination of time extension	press, media, general public		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/extencion-del-proyecto-creasteam https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj/status/1491890729735663621?s=20&t=9PeXqPGs70HBUIAWby1wA
First 2022 meeting. URL	18/02/2022	Dissemination first 2022 meeting	press, media, general public		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/emp-ezamos-el-segundo-ano-del-proyecto-creasteam https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj/status/1484529478772662279?s=20&t=9PeXqPGs70HBUIAWby1wA
Teacher training. URL	23/02/2022	Dissemination to teachers. Mobility STEAM, robotics, training	press, media, general public		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/proyecto-europeo-de-formacion-en-steam-social-y-robotica-educativa-por-profesorado https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj/status/1497326551091789830?s=20&t=9PeXqPGs70HBUIAWby1wA
2nd Transnational Meeting. URL	25/02/2022	Dissemination of the 2nd Transnational Meeting	press, media, general public		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/2o-encuentro-transnacional-presencial-del-proyecto-creasteam
Teacher training. URL	25/03/2022	Dissemination to teachers. Mobility STEAM, robotics, training	press, media, general public		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/segunda-formacion-steam-y-robotica-para-escuelas-italianas https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj/status/1507359915668553733?s=20&t=9PeXqPGs70HBUIAWby1wA
Permanent supervisory board meeting. URL	27/05/2022	Dissemination PSB meeting. Summary of the PSB Meeting where key points are presented	press, media, general public		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/reunion-del-permanent-supervisory-board-del-proyecto-creasteam
Teacher training. URL	17/06/2022	Dissemination to teachers. Mobility STEAM, robotics, training	press, media, general public		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/tercer-curso-de-profesores-fdae https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj/status/1537740242257686528?s=20&t=9PeXqPGs70HBUIAWby1wA
PSB-Online Follow UP 3 (pre-Bursa). URL	05/10/2022	Dissemination PSB Meeting	press, media, general public		https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/psb-online-follow-3-pre-bursa-meeting https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj/status/1577582155110252547?s=20&t=9PeXqPGs70HBUIAWby1wA
Teacher training. URL	31/08/2022	Dissemination to teachers. Schools of ARLEL Madrid area	Teachers	30	https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/dise-minacion-al-profesorado-de-infantil-y-primaria-de-salle-madrid https://twitter.com/SalleMadrid/status/1574676012385738754?s=20&t=9PeXqPGs70HBUIAWby1wA

Activity	Date	Brief Description	Target Group	# of people reached	Other data
Teacher training. URL	01/10/2022	Dissemination to teachers. Schools of ARLEP, North Spain area	Teachers	40	https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/dise-minacion-al-profesorado-de-infantil-y-primaria-de-salle-valladolid-del-proyecto-creasteam
Teacher training. URL	8/10/2022	Teacher training in STEAM & diversity gaps. Schools of ARLEP, Catalonia area	Teachers	30	https://blogs.salleurl.edu/es/formacion-de-robotica-y-pensamiento-computacional-profesorado-de-infantil-de-cataluna https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj/status/1580308346304798724?s=20&t=MvZHCyJl9Uv3_QXyKiYgBg
Scientific dissemination. URL	21/10/2022	Dissemination of results of the project in TEEM22 at Salamanca	Teachers and Scientific community	40	https://twitter.com/fonsi1x2/status/1583455809295380480?s=20
3rd Transnational Meeting in BURSA. URL	3rd & 4th/11/2022	Transnational Meeting of the consortium in BURSA.	Partners and associated partners of Turkey.	35	https://twitter.com/fonsi1x2/status/1588055295015763976?s=20 https://twitter.com/aliciagh/status/1588057936626155525?s=20 https://twitter.com/danielamof/status/1588060236035887104?s=20 https://twitter.com/danielamof/status/1588080783620820992?s=20
3rd Transnational Meeting in BURSA. URL	3rd & 4th/11/2022	Transnational Meeting of the consortium in BURSA. Sadettin visit.	Teachers, staff and children	50	https://twitter.com/sadettin_turkun/status/158820326269243392?s=20
3rd Transnational Meeting in BURSA. URL	3rd & 4th/11/2022	Transnational Meeting of the consortium in BURSA. Bursa Innovation center.	Teachers, staff and children	20	https://twitter.com/sadettin_turkun/status/1588108992563355649?s=20 https://twitter.com/bursaimemarge/status/1588260500210561025?s=20
3rd Transnational Meeting in BURSA. URL	3rd & 4th/11/2022	Transnational Meeting of the consortium in BURSA. Mesafe school visit.	Teachers, staff and children	50	https://twitter.com/fonsi1x2/status/1588267894596509696?s=20 https://twitter.com/CreaSTEAM_proj/status/1588441664527667200?s=20 https://twitter.com/fonsi1x2/status/1588441541378707457?s=20 https://twitter.com/fonsi1x2/status/1588626307130175489?s=20
Meeting ARLEP. Barcelona. URL	30/11/2022	Meeting ARLEP Universities and schools for promoting STEAM-Labs	Teachers, and school staff.	8	https://twitter.com/fonsi1x2/status/1598066974248304640?s=20
DivinSTEAM a spin-off of CreaSTEAM. URL	15/3/2023	Presentation of the DivinTech a new project conceptualized in the STEAM_Lab of a Spanish associated school: La Salle La Seu	Teachers, and educational staff of any entity.	30	https://twitter.com/fonsi1x2/status/1625936623052398593?s=20 https://twitter.com/fonsi1x2/status/1625871052470382593?s=20
Final meeting in Salamanca. URL.	22/3/2023	Final meeting of the project in Salamanca (USAL)	Partners and associated schools	20	https://twitter.com/fonsi1x2/status/1638570441546579968?s=20

From a mixed approach to quantify the impact of the dissemination of the project we can resume it with the following data:

INDICATOR	PLANNED	RESULTS
LOCAL AND REGIONAL LEVEL (the relevance of pilots in the schools)		
Schools involved	Minimum 4 schools	13 Schools
Teachers involved	At least 150 teachers	More than 300 teachers
Activities did in the STEAM-Labs	Minimum 30	64 defined and implemented
Students involved in the STEAMLabs	A minimum of 200 students	More than 300 students finished the activities
Students involved directly or indirectly in the activities	A minimum of 550 students	More than 1800 students
NATIONAL LEVEL		
The number of participants in the multiplier events	A minimum of 100 participants	More than 250 participants
The number of organizations and initiatives achieved through dissemination activities	A minimum of 200	The total number contacted will be around 300
The number of schools interested in organizing workshops and activities following the resources and framework related to the STEAM-Labs, and approaches related to foster the Diversity gaps	Not set in the proposal	More than 50 schools contacted and developing STEAM-Labs or join the Unit Plan template
AT INTERNATIONAL LEVEL		
Participation in international conferences to share the main results of the project	Minimum of 4 conferences	6 International conferences
Publication of the results in a formal way	A minimum of 2 indexed publications	4 Publications: 2 published, 1 pending to be publish and 1 pending to be uploaded
Number of other European countries achieved in the dissemination activities:	A minimum of 4 different countries	More than 20 different countries

Other indicators are the average of around 350 views per tweet of the @CreaSTEAM_proj project account, which from its 68 tweets has gained 48 followers, both personal and corporate, highlighting accounts such as @MomandGeekcom, @CatedraTEKHNE, @udigitaledu, @WSTEMproject, @ScoolTic, @FullsEnginyeria, @Cepesa, @CharacterMaker, @docentesdigital, @binomi1, accounts that reflect interests in school improvement, social improvement, teaching aspects and STEAM areas.

Regarding the impact metrics relating to the project website, were collected using dissemination logs, and Google analytics:

- Number of links to the project from other websites: 10
- Number of visitors to the project website: 2322
- Number of repeat visitors to project website: 75
- Average length of time spent on website: 20 seconds.
- Number of sessions opened: 2419
- Maxim number of visits of a webpage: 3137
- Average of pages by session: 1.30

13. Conclusions

Throughout the project, the partners have been active in disseminating the project at all levels, local, regional, national, and international, both at the educational level and in terms of relations between entities and scientific dissemination activities. The objectives established in terms of potential centers, users, and the target public, have been far exceeded, which allows us to affirm that on the one hand the interest in the proposal is important and on the other hand that the activity carried out has been adequate.

Overall, we can affirm that the CreaSTEAM project has achieved the defined objectives, both the main objectives of the defined Intellectual Outputs, as well as the secondary ones linked to maintaining the quality and dissemination of its activities, highlighting the high level and impact of teacher training. In this sense, the strategy carried out seems replicable in future projects, both for members of this consortium and others.

